

**DELIVERABLE D5.1 –
Dissemination, Exploitation,
Communication Plan – V1**

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Abbreviations

- CENAM** – Centre for Nanotechnology and Advanced Materials
- CEPLANT** – R&D centre for plasma and nanotechnology surface modifications
- CU** – Comenius University
- ERDF** – European Regional Development Fund
- EU** – European Union
- FAS** – Faculty of Applied Sciences
- FMPI** – Faculty of Mathematics, Physics and Informatics
- FP** – Framing programme
- GA** – Grant agreement
- HE** – Horizon Europe
- HR** – Human resources
- KPIs** – Key performance indicators
- MU** – Masaryk University
- NTIS** – New Technologies for the Information Society – European centre of excellence
- R&D** – Research and development
- R&I** – Research and innovation
- RMA** – Research managers and administrators
- UWB** – University of West Bohemia
- WP** – Work package

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Executive summary

This document provides a detailed plan for the dissemination, exploitation, and communication of the activities carried out in the COLOSSE project. The communication strategy describes the objectives, identifies target groups and strategic activities, and links them to COLOSSE's key performance indicators. The document also presents communication tools and channels for capturing target groups. The document presents the website, connections to social networks, and the press in this context. The plan defines the visual identity in the form of the project logo, presentation templates, and a detailed graphic manual. The dissemination and exploitation strategy presents suitable pathways for delivering key messages related to the COLOSSE project to target groups. The document proposes indicators for monitoring impact in individual communication channels. Finally, the plan presents ways of using the outputs achieved in the COLOSSE project in relation to intellectual property.

Key words

COLOSSE, dissemination, exploitation, communication, industry, academia, citizens, visual identity, website, social media, graphic manual, impact

1 Introduction

The goal of COLOSSE is to increase the participation of Czech and Slovak plasma-enabled surface engineering R&I centres in Horizon Europe and future EU Framework Programmes for R&I. The project connects three institutions: Masaryk University in Brno, the University of West Bohemia in Pilsen, and Comenius University in Bratislava.

To achieve the goal, we will focus on 4 specific objectives:

- Strengthen the connections of COLOSSE centres to world-leading R&I centres
- Build conditions that will enable internationalization of human resources
- Develop skill-set that enables interdisciplinary and intersectoral collaboration and facilitates creativity
- Enable sustainability of the COLOSSE partnership through synergic use ERDF and HE/FP resources

The three centres have joined together to promote our publicity and visibility on the European R&D field map. Together, we will extend good research practices by recruiting new post-doc staff from abroad and presenting our research activities at European R&D centres, conferences, and trade fairs. We also plan to organize hard- and soft-skills training, as well as two PhD retreat conferences with international overlap for our early-stage researchers and doctoral students.

Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan objectives are:

- Ensure visibility of the Project activities and results within the consortium organisations
- Ensure visibility of the Project activities and results beyond the consortium
- Increase the visibility of COLOSSE technology inventory and collaboration offer across industry and academia in Europe and beyond
- Communicate the potential applications and innovations enabled by plasma-enhanced surface engineering to a broader audience
- Engage citizens by communicating information on technological advances in a clear and accessible way and by highlighting the societal impact and importance of publicly funded research

Communication management

The communication team is composed by the leader from CU who coordinates the communication actions and takes care of the implementation of the activities, and representatives from each partner.

The dissemination and communication strategy of COLOSSE has two main dimensions:

- External, it will be guided to a large extent by the internationalization strategy developed under WP1 but will also be relevant when piloting postdoctoral career scheme under WP2.
- Internal, where we see the need to emphasize project communication towards the staff of COLOSSE centres, researchers and RMAs of COLOSSE centres. We need to engage researchers and RMAs from the project consortium to proactively reach for the benefits presented by skill development under WP2 and project development under WP3.

2 Communication strategy

Main message for all target groups: “Plasma-enabled surface engineering is facilitating technological advancement from medicine, through environmental sustainability, to space exploration. COLOSSE is funded by the EU.”

2.1. Target groups

The main target groups of our efforts are:

2.1.1. Industry

segmented into companies (a) working on plasma technologies and (b) using plasma technologies to enhance their products in other sectors. Thanks to COLOSSE, our skills and technologies will be known and available more broadly to companies outside of Czechia and Slovakia. This, however, will also be a major benefit for our local and regional partner companies, because they may also be taken aboard in international projects along with the COLOSSE centres, and thus enhance their own networks.

2.1.2. Academia

(a) Researchers from outside of Czechia and Slovakia will be able to tap into the equipment and talent pool of COLOSSE thanks to increasing internationalization. (b) Researchers of the COLOSSE centres will increase their competences through training and enhance their collaborative networks. (c) Research managers and administrators (RMA)s from the consortium will acquire skills enabling them to support HE/FP proposals and projects.

2.1.3. Citizens

They are the ultimate beneficiaries of innovation enabled by advances in surface engineering. We will seek to communicate technological advances in an understandable way to showcase what are the end-results of public funding of research and why it is an important investment for our society.

2.2. Key messages

2.2.1. Industry

(a, b) Invite to collaborate – list of equipment and services available at the COLOSSE centres incl. modalities of access.

(a, b) Share research results.

(a, b) Invite selected companies to workshops on project development.

2.2.2. Academia

(a) Invite to collaborate – list of equipment and services available at the COLOSSE centres incl. modalities of access.

(a) Advertise open postdoc positions.

(a) Invite young researchers (i.e. early stage researchers) from our strategic partners to join the events

(b, c) Inform about project activities and achievements.

2.2.3. Citizens

Inform about project activities and achievements.

Present training and research activities and opportunities available at the COLOSSE centres.

2.3. Communication channels

2.3.1. Project website

Design a dedicated [website](#) for the COLOSSE platform. Inform about project objectives, consortium, and planned work. Post all events and calls. Post news on achievements of the project. Dedicated section on technology inventory and collaboration offers of the COLOSSE platform.

Website will be kept open for at least 3 years after the project end. The impact of the project will be highlighted continuously (e.g. HE/FP projects awarded after the end-date of COLOSSE will recognize the support of the project).

2.3.2. Local university webpages

- Masaryk University

Masaryk University: <https://www.muni.cz/en>

Faculty of Science, Masaryk University: <https://www.sci.muni.cz/en>

Physics departments at Masaryk University: <https://www.physics.muni.cz/en>

Department of Plasma Physics and Technology, SCI MUNI:

<https://www.physics.muni.cz/en/departments/dppt>

CEPLANT (R&D centre for plasma and nanotechnology surface modifications):

<https://ceplant.cz/>

- Comenius University Bratislava

Comenius University: <https://uniba.sk/en/>

Faculty of Mathematics, Physics and Informatics, CU: <https://fmph.uniba.sk/en>

CENAM: <https://fmph.uniba.sk/en/departments/centre-for-nanotechnology-and-advanced-materials/>

- University of West Bohemia

University of West Bohemia: <https://www.zcu.cz/en/index.html>

Faculty of Applied Sciences: <https://www.fav.zcu.cz/en/>

Department of Physics: <https://www.kfy.zcu.cz/en/>

New Technologies for the Information Society (NTIS):

<https://www.ntis.zcu.cz/en/Research/New-nanostructured-thin-film-materials/index.html>

2.3.3. Social media

We will use current accounts (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, etc.) of COLOSSE centres and their universities and will inform about events and achievements linking to project website. We created a Facebook page and Instagram account COLOSSE to secure the names. The accounts are not public but are ready to be used if needed.

- Facebook

Department of Plasma Physics and Technology:

<https://www.facebook.com/ustavUFTP>

CEPLANT: <https://www.facebook.com/ceplantbrno/>

FMPI CU: <https://www.facebook.com/MatFyzJelIn>

UWB: <https://www.facebook.com/FAV.ZCU>

- LinkedIn

COLOSSE: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/colosse2024/>

Department of Plasma Physics and Technology:

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/86256893/>

CEPLANT: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/103788240>

UWB: <https://cz.linkedin.com/company/ntis-new-technologies-for-the-information-society>

- Instagram

Department of Plasma Physics and Technology –

https://www.instagram.com/uftp_sci_muni/

FMPI CU: <https://www.instagram.com/matfyzjein/>

UWB: <https://www.instagram.com/fav.zcu/>

Hashtags that we plan to use:

Project in general:

#COLOSSE #EuropeanCommission #HorizonEu #HorizonEurope #Synergies
#ResearchImpactEU

Personal resources:

#postdoc #PhD #scientist #researcher #physicist

Scientific:

- General: #technology #science #tech #plasma #ThinFilms #physics #nanotechnology #MaterialsResearch #MaterialScience
- Specific coatings: #sputtering #HiPIMS #ThinFilmDeposition #magnetron #MagnetronSputtering #pvd #VacuumCoating #coatings
- Specific analysis: #microscopy

2.3.4. Press

Release will be published shortly after the kick-off meeting. Afterwards, we will focus on addressing media with the opportunity to publish interviews with leading researchers or incoming postdocs from the COLOSSE centres.

2.4. Visual identity

As part of the project, we have developed a dedicated logo that will be used consistently across all communication materials. In addition, we have also prepared templates for presentations, documents, and other outputs to ensure a cohesive visual identity (see Annex 1 Design manual).

Figure 1 COLOSSE logo in different colours

Figure 2 COLOSSE presentation template

In line with the requirements outlined in the Grant Agreement (Article 17), all materials will prominently feature the EU logo, along with a statement acknowledging the financial support from the European Union and disclaimer.

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Figure 3 European flag and funding statement

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Figure 4 Disclaimer

3 Dissemination and exploitation strategy

Dissemination and exploitation activities will ensure that results will be made visible to the appropriate communities of users and practitioners who can benefit from their application.

The main target groups with key messages and dissemination channels to maximise their impact are listed below.

3.1. Target group 1a: Industry – companies developing and producing plasma-enabled surface engineering solutions

Message: COLOSSE is a reliable partner for collaboration, either in joint projects funded by public resources, or for delivery of contract research. COLOSSE produces basic research results with strong application potential in plasma sources and plasma diagnostics.

Dedicated dissemination pathways:

- COLOSSE Technology inventory and collaboration offer: list of equipment and services available at the COLOSSE centres incl. modalities of access (e.g. CEPLANT equipment is available in open access mode thanks to funding from a national large research infrastructures scheme).

- Industry networks & associations: as outlined in Section 1.2.3 of GA, we have access to a number of plasmatech- focused networks on the interface of academia and industry (INPLAS, BalticNet, Graphene Council). We will publish and spread especially the COLOSSE Technology inventory and collaboration offer, but also ad hoc relevant results, through these networks.
- Participation in conferences and technology trade fairs: we will present the infrastructure, expertise and results of COLOSSE at venues where the worlds of academia and industry meet, e.g. PSE, ICMCTF.
- Final dissemination workshop: we will hand-pick companies where we see strong collaboration potential and invite them to participate in the final workshop.
- Project development: where relevant, we will seek to involve key industrial collaborators into the development of R&I priorities selected in WP3 from the very beginning. Thus, we plan to address them with concrete outlines for future projects, including potential funding sources, and invite them to the project development workshops.

3.2. Target group 1b: Industry – companies using surface engineering to improve their products in diverse fields of industry

Message: Surface engineering solutions are an excellent tool to increase product quality and value. COLOSSE is a reliable partner for development of tailored surface engineering solutions. COLOSSE offers outstanding infrastructure to test novel surface engineering approaches.

Dedicated dissemination pathways:

- COLOSSE Technology inventory and collaboration offer: same as target group 1a.
- Industry networks & associations: as outlined in Section 1.2.3 of GA, we already promote our services in broadly-targeted platforms (Technology Centres for KETs). We will publish and spread especially the COLOSSE Technology inventory and collaboration offer, but also ad hoc relevant results, through such networks, and continuously seek new platforms for promotion of our facilities.
- Participation in conferences and technology trade fairs: we will reach out of the innovation community focused on plasma technologies and present ourselves at events in diverse areas of manufacturing, with tailored showcase of relevant research results and infrastructure. We foresee to promote COLOSSE collaboration opportunities for automotive, electronics,

optics, energy, space, or biomedical companies.

- Project development: end-users of engineered surfaces will be essential partners in consortia of newly developed projects resulting from COLOSSE activities. We identify and address relevant companies to match the R&I priorities selected for project development in WP3 in coordination with strategic academic partners. We will invite the end-user companies to project development workshops where they are essential for the core of the project concept.

3.3. Target group 2a: Academia – researchers working in fields related to plasma-enabled surface engineering outside of Czechia and Slovakia

Message: COLOSSE is a reliable partner for collaboration. COLOSSE harbours unique equipment and expertise and is ready to contribute with it to R&I projects that can benefit from plasma-enabled surface engineering. COLOSSE can deliver creative solutions to address difficult research questions. COLOSSE provides excellent environment for research careers of researchers originating anywhere in the world, of any gender and nationality, from PhD students through postdocs towards independent principal investigators.

Dedicated dissemination pathways:

- COLOSSE Technology inventory and collaboration offer: same as target group 1a.
- Participation in scientific conferences: we will join the internationally leading venues of scientific knowledge exchange with presentations of research results of the COLOSSE centres. We foresee participation in conferences such as conferences organized by IUVSTA.
- Academic recruitment portals: we will advertise open postdoc positions in portals such as Euraxess, ResearchGate, IEEE, or American Vacuum Society (AVS).
- Final dissemination workshop: we will hand-pick companies where we see strong collaboration potential and invite them to participate in the final workshop.
- Research secondments to advanced partners: especially with our strategic partners, we will build trust in the competence of COLOSSE centres through direct engagement in joint research. WPI will support international mobility of researchers, who will be the envoys of our reputation.
- Young researchers' retreats: we will selectively invite young researchers (i.e. early stage researchers) from our strategic partners to join the events, and

thus the early-career networks which they will then be able to carry with them as they progress to senior positions in academia and industry.

- Project development: we intend to involve especially the strategic partners, but also other academic stakeholders based on scientific and technological needs, in project development activities of WP3. We will identify and address suitable partners individually.
- Publications in high-quality peer-review journals: While not being produced directly by project activities, the COLOSSE efforts will contribute to quality increase of scientific publications (due to working with strategic partners, development of human resources etc.). This indirect effect is still essential for improving the reputation and collaborative potential of COLOSSE centres, since they are academic institutions and cores of future projects will still mostly comprise academic institutions.

3.4. Target group 2b and 2c: Academia – researchers at the COLOSSE centres; research managers and administrators at the COLOSSE centres

Message: The COLOSSE project represents a unique opportunity to advance research careers through training on scientific and soft skills and through enhancement of networks. For research leaders: COLOSSE represents an excellent venue to diversify and strengthen funding portfolio by development of international projects.

Dedicated dissemination pathways:

- Project newsletter: twice a year, we will summarize the news and opportunities presented by COLOSSE in a newsletter to be distributed by the pathways defined below.
- Direct mailing: we will keep track of relevant groups of researchers and create a mailing list encompassing those that have the highest potential to benefit from the project. This is feasible bearing in mind that the directly involved research teams are well-defined and not excessively broad. These researchers will be addressed directly with relevant training and networking opportunities.
- Internal communication platforms: being embedded in universities, the COLOSSE centres benefit from dedicated platforms enabling internal communication (e.g. MUNI Portal). We will use these platforms to spread news and opportunities of the project.

3.5. Target group 3: Citizens – general public with interest in science, including opinion leaders and policy makers that contribute to development of environment for research and innovation in Czechia, Slovakia, and Europe

Message: COLOSSE is a technological flagship contributing to our well-being. Careers in science, technology, and engineering, in the COLOSSE centres, are fascinating and should be first choice for every talented student with curious mind.

Dedicated dissemination pathways:

- European Researchers' Night, European Women Researchers' Day, International Day of Women and Girls in Science in February: involvement in broader set of events organized at the level of universities. Special focus on promoting science and engineering careers towards girls and women, who are underrepresented in research staff of the COLOSSE centres.
- Open days: we will actively present training and research opportunities available at the COLOSSE centres in the open day events organized by our universities and faculties.
- Popular science articles: we will publish articles on what can be achieved by plasma technologies and also simplified background on the scientific and technological principles employed in surface modifications.

4 Impact monitoring

The dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities will be implemented within WP5. Where the performance of our dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities is not tracked directly by the main result KPIs of the project, we introduce dedicated indicators: DEC KPIs.

DEC KPI	Target
participation in plasma technology oriented events	3
participants from industry (final dissemination workshop)	5
participation at technology-oriented events without main focus on plasma technologies	6
participations in scientific conferences	9
newsletters	6
popular science articles	3
press articles	4
project webpage available and constantly updated	yes
logo and visual identity of the project visible on the website and in all the project materials	yes
social media: LinkedIn posts	3 per month

Table 1 Dedicated indicators

Perspective impact pathways for actual project results will be designed during preparation of next versions of this plan (M15, M36).

5 Intellectual Property Management

The project will not generate any research results, but will facilitate their creation e.g. by mobility and recruitment, and thus we will seek to ensure that the indirectly supported results adhere to principles of sound intellectual property (IP) management. First of all, on mobility, researchers supported by COLOSSE will retain their employee status to their universities, so the results they generate will be (co-) owned by their employers – MUNI, CU, or UWB. We will outline the basic principles for ownership of results in bi-lateral agreements with the secondment hosts and seek to formalize IP arrangements with our strategic partners in a coherent manner for

a longer period of time. In case of joint work among COLOSSE beneficiaries, the IPR management will be guided by Consortium Agreement based on the DESCA model.

In project development activities, we will seek to enter with the participants into non-disclosure agreements (NDA), if we aim for commercially viable products. Generally, we will however seek to be as open as possible and only as closed as necessary. And given the nature of the direct project results, we foresee that it will be possible to keep a high level of openness overall. An exception may be some presentation during early-stage researchers' retreats, where researchers may openly discuss unpublished data, or training materials whether we will involve external lecturers.

6 Annexes

6.1. Design manual

Design Manual

Logo

Logo color

- R 0, G 139, B 202
C 97%, M 29%, Y 3%, K 0%
008bca

- R 236, G 0, B 140
C 0%, M 100%, Y 0%, K 0%
ec008c
- R 0, G 174, B 239
C 100%, M 0%, Y 0%, K 0%
00aeef
- R 0, G 86, B 160
C 100%, M 74%, Y 5%, K 0%
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Roll-up

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Surface Engineering

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Paper

Title page

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Poppins Regular

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C 0%, M 0%, Y 0%, K 100%
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Poppins Bold

R 0, G 0, B 0
C 0%, M 0%, Y 0%, K 0%
ffffff

Background

R 236, G 0, B 140
C 0%, M 100%, Y 0%, K 0%
ec008c

Social networks

Instagram

Facebook

LinkedIn

T-shirt

Digital print

Screen printing